

Digital Multimeters Voltage Sampling Performance Comparison

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Abstract—This article evaluates the sampling performance of the Fluke 8588A digital multimeter, introduced in 2019, and compares it to that of the Keysight 3458A, well established in metrology laboratories. We measured the frequency and phase response, as well as noise contributions from timing jitter, 1/f noise, and frequency-independent noise for all DC voltage ranges. The results show that the capabilities and performance of the two multimeters vary significantly depending on the operating modes and parameters selected for the measurement. This analysis reveals that the Fluke 8588A introduces a new set of performance tradeoffs rather than being a direct replacement for the Keysight 3458A.

Index Terms—Amplitude response, harmonics, Josephson voltage source, measurement, measurement uncertainty, phase response, sampling.

I. INTRODUCTION

SOON after Hewlett Packard introduced the 3458A (DMM1) digital multimeter in 1988, metrologists in National Metrology Institutes (NMI) started using its novel sampling capabilities, groundbreaking performance increases, particularly in terms of lowering uncertainties [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7] in various measurement areas. This was achieved by using a custom-made multislope integrating analog-to-digital converter (IADC), which exhibits a few key properties built in by design. First, the IADC has variable resolution, which is a function of a programmable aperture time. Second, the aperture time itself provides a calculable filter that effectively attenuates high-frequency signals before they can interfere with the resulting quantization process. Third, this filter function can be corrected almost exactly even for large

ratios up to 5000:1 [1]. DMM1 became the state of the art for sampling low-frequency signals [8].

The IADC technique has since evolved into a widely popular delta-sigma conversion technique [9]. The NI-5922 flexible resolution digitizer became popular in many NMIs for performing state-of-the-art measurements, and it arguably offers the top performance that delta-sigma conversion techniques can deliver. However, its performance never challenged the DMM1 performance for low-frequency sampling applications. After three decades, the Fluke 8588A (DMM2) appears to be the first DMM in almost 30 years to challenge the state-of-the-art DMM1 sampling performance. A short performance comparison was reported in [10]. A comprehensive evaluation of DMM1 sampling performance with comparison to DMM2 is presented in this article, which is an extension of the preceding paper [10]. As this evaluation only deals with sampling voltage signals, it can in no case prejudice the complete performance of any instrument discussed.

A precision ČMI SWG03 DDS source [11] and Keysight 33622A arbitrary waveform synthesizer [12] were used for all measurements requiring sine wave input signals.

II. ADC TECHNOLOGY

A. DMM ADC

DMMs are primarily intended to accurately measure voltage, current, resistance, and possibly other quantities. To achieve this, the ADC used must be stable, linear, and have a high resolution, while a high conversion speed is not required. The ADC technology of choice is an integrating or charge balance ADC (IADC), dominating the DMM market for decades. Its multislope version, developed for the Hewlett-Packard DMM1 provided for an unprecedented performance increase in stability, linearity, and resolution. Importantly, this was not sacrificed by an excessively slow performance. On the contrary, also the maximum sampling rate was increased from a solid 1350 Hz in the previous model (HP 3457A) [13] to a then whopping 100 kHz for an IADC while still maintaining 16 bit resolution [14]. To cope with even higher frequency repetitive signals, the sample-hold circuitry is employed to freeze a signal until it is converted by its IADC. This circuitry allows for only 50 kHz sampling frequency, but a short aperture time of 2 ns allows for a subsampling scheme, technically employing 100 MHz sampling rate and capturing repetitive signals with frequencies approaching 50 MHz. However, this sample-hold measurement path is far less accurate than a direct DCV path.

Received 18 November 2025; accepted 16 February 2026. Date of publication 4 March 2026; date of current version 20 March 2026. This work was supported in part by the Project 22RPT02 True8DIGIT through the European Partnership on Metrology from the European Unions' Horizon Europe Research and Innovation program and the Participating States, in part by U.K. participant in Horizon Europe Project 22RPT02 True8DIGIT through UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) (Signal Conversion Ltd.) under Grant 10084012, and in part by the Institutional Subsidy for Long-Term Conceptual Development of a Research Organization granted to the Czech Metrology Institute by the Ministry of Industry and Trade. The Associate Editor coordinating the review process was Dr. Helko E. van den Brom. (*Corresponding author: Boštjan Voljč.*)

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Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/TIM.2026.3670543

DMM2 introduces a slightly different concept, using IADC (or Charge Balancing ADC or CB) for slow sampling rates up to 4,7619 kHz and an 18 bit successive approximation (SAR) ADC for fast sampling rates up to 5 MHz. Additionally, as a newer product, DMM2 offers much larger internal memory (15 M samples) and a set of interfaces for transferring commands and data (GPIB, USB, and Ethernet). The CB and SAR technologies are said to work together [15] for the best precision and best digitisation, but it is not disclosed either how this is implemented nor what the actual benefits are, except for actually covering combined sampling rates from 0,1 Hz up to 5 MHz. DMM2 actually provides for three modes of operation [15], [16].

- 1) CB mode can be used for aperture times from $100 \mu\text{s}$ up to 10 s, with minimum trigger interval equal to aperture time plus $170 \mu\text{s}$. $25 \mu\text{s}$ is used for balancing zero before the measurement aperture, and $85 \mu\text{s}$ is used afterward for subreference ramps of the multislope operation. There seems to be an additional $60 \mu\text{s}$ necessary for the internal processing before a new valid trigger can be accepted. The CB mode is the most stable and the most accurate mode of operation [17].
- 2) SAR mode can be used for aperture times below $100 \mu\text{s}$ down to “zero” aperture time. Here, the aperture is emulated by averaging the required number of samples from the SAR ADC, which is internally sampling at 5 MHz sample rate. Additional $30 \mu\text{s}$ is required for each averaged conversion, yielding a highest sampling frequency of 33.333 kHz. The use of this additional $30 \mu\text{s}$ time is not disclosed.
- 3) DIGITIZE (DIG) mode employs the SAR DAC directly, without any additional delays, enabling the full 5 MHz sampling speed. Aperture time is still programmable from 0 ns to 3 ms, and it uses the same technique as in SAR mode to emulate the analog CB aperture time function. Manufacturer voltage accuracy specifications [17] for SAR mode and digitizing mode are virtually the same.

B. DMM Sampling Resolution

The sampling resolution discussed in this report refers to the ADC quantisation resolution and not to the usual DMM resolution specification, which also includes other imperfections like differential nonlinearity and noise [18]. The sampling resolution can be easily determined by reading a scale factor which is used to convert binary values back to voltage values [19]. This was used to retrieve the DMM1 sampling resolution, but was not a useful approach for DMM2, as this function was not working on the available pair of DMM2. Alternatively, a number of samples were taken with input terminals shorted, and the record was sorted from the lowest to the highest value measured. The minimum step was easily retrieved, indicating the ADC numerical resolution at a number of aperture times selected. The retrieved sampling resolution for both DMMs is shown in Fig. 1. The SAR sampling resolution increases with the increasing aperture time, as the averaging function provides for the otherwise fixed SAR ADC resolution increase.

Fig. 1. DMM analog-to-digital converter resolution in bits for nominal range input level. Circles denote points in which this resolution was extracted from sampled data. For DMM1, this was achieved on more points, which are not indicated on this graph.

Further, DMM2 provides for a higher sampling resolution than DMM1 from $100 \mu\text{s}$ to 30 ms aperture time. However, from 4 ms aperture time and longer, the DMM2 limits the CB ADC resolution at 28 bits, while DMM1 limit is imposed at 32 bits. Again, the sampling resolution described here does not provide any meaningful DMM performance parameter, but it provides an upper limit of internal ADC resolving power and perhaps a glimpse of its internal operation.

III. DMM NOISE PERFORMANCE

There is a difference in the DMM2 design that has to be noted here to better understand the performance being reported later on. Its CB mode signal path 28 kHz bandwidth is much lower than the DMM1’s DCV 150 kHz bandwidth. This would, in principle, reduce the overall noise of the DMM, with the price paid for the limited frequency response linearity at low frequencies. Further, DMM2 employs zero stabilization to achieve superior offset performance [15]. This would push the $1/f$ noise (pink noise) and $1/f^2$ noise (drift) corner frequencies to much lower values, but could potentially degrade the overall signal-to-noise ratio. DMM1 can use auto-zero operation mode to mitigate pink noise and drift issues, but at the expense of reduced sampling frequency.

A. Signal-to-Noise Ratio

The signal-to-noise ratio was measured by short-circuiting the input terminals and performing sampling at different aperture times. 128 samples were taken in a sample burst, and three bursts were taken to further average the result at each aperture time. Sampling frequencies were chosen so as to cancel the mains signal frequency interference. From the burst samples, the noise voltage σ_n was estimated as a median value of the FFT spectrum noise amplitude, thus rejecting interference signals originating from the mains frequency signal or other sources producing steady frequency signals. The SNR was finally calculated as a ratio of nominal range rms voltage $R/\sqrt{2}$ to the noise voltage

$$SNR = \frac{R}{\sigma_n \sqrt{2}}. \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. 100 mV range signal-to-noise ratio.

Fig. 5. 100 V range signal-to-noise ratio.

Fig. 3. 1 V range signal-to-noise ratio.

Fig. 6. 1 kV range signal-to-noise ratio.

Fig. 4. 10 V range signal-to-noise ratio.

Results show a performance difference in signal-to-noise ratio between DMM1 (DCV mode, no auto zero) [20] and DMM2 (CB mode) DMMs (see Figs. 2–6). At aperture times from $100\ \mu\text{s}$ up to $10\ \text{ms}$, the DMM1 SNR is larger from 20 to 15 dB on 10 V and 1 kV ranges. This difference is smaller in other ranges where the input stage amplifiers play

a more dominant role. From aperture time at around $100\ \mu\text{s}$ and up, the SNR of DMM1 stops increasing and actually starts to decrease due to increasing $1/f$ noise [19], while the SNR of DMM2 increases further up to 161.4 dB, being actually limited by the 28 bit resolution limit of the CB analog-to-digital converter. It should be noted here that DMM1 does not employ auto-zero functionality in this comparison. The DMM2 DIG SNR performance, which was found to be virtually identical to its SAR performance at aperture times below $100\ \mu\text{s}$, shows a slower increase with increasing aperture time. Nevertheless, the SNR in DIG mode is better than in CB mode for all aperture times available for DIG mode (up to $3\ \text{ms}$, except in 100 mV range, where the input amplifier reduces the SNR in DIG mode by 20 dB across all aperture times).

Noise measurements on DMM1 10V range were confirmed using a Josephson Junction source at 0, 10, and $-10\ \text{V}$. The noise floor was higher by 0.57 dB at 10 and $-10\ \text{V}$ input voltage compared to 0 V input voltage.

B. $1/f$ Noise and Drift

Drift and $1/f$ noise were investigated using linear spectral densities following the Welch method [21], using overlapping

Fig. 7. 100 mV range noise spectral density.

Fig. 9. 10 V range noise spectral density.

Fig. 8. 1 V range noise spectral density.

Fig. 10. 100 V range noise spectral density.

Hanning windows as used in [22]. The number of samples in each time series of measured data was chosen to effectively cover the frequency of interest down to 1 MHz with a fixed sampling time of 9 ms. Time series were captured by each DMM with their input terminals short-circuited, using the internal timer to dictate the sampling time. Leakage from DC was avoided by subtracting the mean value of the time series.

Linear spectral density results are shown in Figs. 7–11 as a function of frequency. They are collected together for each of the five DMM ranges and cover six responses each.

- 1) DMM1 IADC AZERO OFF response at 3 ms aperture time and 9 ms sampling time, except for 100 V and 1 kV ranges, where the sampling time was increased to 18 ms.
- 2) DMM1 IADC AZERO ON response (AZ) at 3 ms aperture time and 9 ms sampling time, except for 100 V and 1 kV ranges, where the sampling time was increased to 18 ms.
- 3) DMM2 CB response at 3 ms aperture time and 9 ms sampling time.
- 4) DMM2 CB response at 199 ms aperture time and 200 ms sampling time.

- 5) DMM2 SAR response at 99.8 μ s aperture time and 9 ms sampling time.
- 6) DMM2 DIG response at 3 ms aperture time and 9 ms sampling time.

Frequency spikes between 10 and 55.6 Hz are a by-product of mains voltage frequency components and possibly other internal DMM or external sources and can be ignored in terms of pink noise and drift analysis. DMM2 clearly has a stronger white noise component compared to DMM1 at 3 ms aperture time, supporting the measurements and discussion from the previous chapter. However, DMM2 excels in $1/f$ corner frequency, which is pushed down to 10 MHz or so on 100 mV range, and further down to 1 MHz or so on all other ranges. Nevertheless, DMM1 with auto zero function enabled (AZ), which more than doubles the required sampling time, provides superior performance with an expected 3 dB penalty noise increase compared to auto zero function disabled. It appears that the DMM2 SAR mode is much more noisy than DMM2 DIG mode, presumably due to the CB zero operation that precedes each measurement in this mode and adds its own noise to the final result. The $1/f$ or $1/f^2$ corner frequency for DMM2 DIG and DMM2 SAR modes seems to be one order of magnitude or so lower than $1/f$ corner frequency for DMM1 without using auto zero. DMM1 can mitigate this deficiency

Fig. 11. 1 kV range noise spectral density.

Fig. 12. 10 V range overlapped Allan deviation.

quite effectively using the auto-zero mode, at the expense of longer sampling time for a given aperture time, limiting the highest sampling frequency to below 4 kHz and 3 dB noise increase [19].

When the application allows for it, these penalties can be mitigated further by using short sampling bursts where each burst starts with a single auto-zero cycle, which is not repeated during the sampling burst [23], [24]. This can be effectively implemented using internal DMM1 auto-zero event functionality [19]. While this technique was not tested in this study, its effectiveness for $1/f$ noise and drift cancellation depends on the short sampling burst duration and shall be checked on a case-by-case basis.

For an additional presentation of the low-frequency noise behavior in a time-series of measured data, an overlapped Allan deviations [25], [26] for 10 V range data are plotted in Fig. 12.

C. Jitter Noise

Jitter noise appears in a sampled signal as a consequence of sample timing variations [27]. A signal-to-noise ratio due to a random sampling time jitter is given by

$$SNR_j = -20 \cdot \log_{10}(2\pi f t_j) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 13. DMM1 and DMM2 jitter noise induced signal-to-noise ratio roll-off. Circles represent measured SNR while the lines represent fits to (3). (a) DMM2 in CB mode (sample: TIMER), (b) DMM2 in SAR mode (sample: TIMER), (c) DMM2 in DIG mode (sample: TIMER), (d) DMM1 in DCV mode (sample: TIMER), and (e) DMM1 in DCV mode (sample: EXT). DMM1 in DCV mode using a master-slave synchronization is not plotted as it is virtually identical to (e).

TABLE I

ESTIMATED EFFECTIVE JITTER NOISE VALUES FROM RESULTS PLOTTED IN FIG. 13. t_s AND t_a ARE SAMPLING PARAMETERS USED FOR EACH DMM AND MODE COMBINATION MEASUREMENTS

DMM	Mode	Timebase used	t_s	t_a	t_j
DMM1	DCV	Timer	10 μ s	1 μ s	145 ps
DMM1	DCV	External	10 μ s	1 μ s	6 ns
DMM1	DCV	Master-Slave	10 μ s	1 μ s	6.8 ns
DMM2	CB	Timer or External	20 μ s	110 μ s	100 ns
DMM2	SAR	Timer or External	30 μ s	0 s	493 ps
DMM2	DIG	Timer or External	200 ns	0 s	≤ 7.7 ps

where f is signal frequency and t_j is a standard deviation of the time jitter. SNR_j defined here is referenced to the signal amplitude applied, from where it is clear that the jitter noise does not exist if there is no signal applied. From (2) it follows that for increasing signal frequency the SNR_j will drop by 20 dB per decade. The combined SNR_c is given by

$$SNR_c = -20 \cdot \log_{10} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_n}{V}\right)^2 + (2\pi f t_j)^2} \quad (3)$$

where σ_n is a white noise rms voltage. σ_n limits the highest achievable SNR_c , which starts to roll down as the SNR_j becomes the dominant SNR_c component.

Measurements were performed by using fixed DMM sample parameters in each mode and sampling full-scale input sine wave signal at different frequencies. The shortest available aperture times were used so that aperture roll-off would not affect measurement results. It is further important that the sine wave amplitude remains flat within approximately ± 0.5 dB over the whole tested frequency range. Additionally, it is important that the source SNR at highest frequencies remains higher than the measured SNR as estimated from the sampled values. That would assure that the DMM jitter and not the source jitter is measured. A Keysight 33622A arbitrary waveform synthesizer with amplitude flatness of ± 0.25 dB

Fig. 15. IADC and averaging frequency response as a function of normalized frequency, where integration time t_a for IADC (red curve) equals the averaging time t_{ad} for SAR. $Q = 100$, $t_a = t_{ad} = t_{sd}/Q$. Up to $\bar{f} \approx 0.1$ Hz/Hz, $H_{t_{ad}} \approx H_{t_a}$.

TABLE II

NOMINAL FREQUENCY BANDWIDTHS FOR DMM2 VOLTAGE SAMPLING MODES. VALUES MARKED WITH * ARE NOT SPECIFIED BY A MANUFACTURER

Mode	Filter	f_{3dB}	filter poles
CB	-	13.8 kHz*	1
SAR	-	100 kHz*	1
DIG	100 kHz	100 kHz	1
DIG	3 MHz	3 MHz	4
DIG	Off	15 MHz - 20 MHz	-

Fig. 15 plots both H_a and H_{ad} for the case $t_a = t_{ad}$ for 100 samples being used for one averaging measurement result ($Q = 100$).

B. Input Filter Roll-Off

For frequencies up to 20 kHz, the DMM1 input filter amplitude response is often modeled with a single pole RC filter [1]

$$H_{1p} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{f}{f_{3dB}}\right)^2}}. \quad (14)$$

Since its amplitude response was already shown to closely resemble the DMM response up to a few kHz [30], despite the input circuitry actually consists of two equal serially connected RC networks with 1% tolerance 5 k Ω resistors and 2% tolerance 82 pF capacitors. The single-pole RC filter model would imply phase response

$$\Phi_{1p} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{f}{f_{3dB}} \right). \quad (15)$$

The DMM2 nominal frequency response depends on the sampling mode and is collected in Table II for 10 V range. Measured frequency responses for 1 V to 1 kV ranges, and modes for both DMM types are plotted in Figs. 16 and 17. All measurements were performed by applying a sine wave from an arbitrary waveform synthesizer at selected frequencies and estimating a measured amplitude using an asynchronous PSFE

Fig. 16. 1 and 10 V range frequency responses. The DMM2 digitizing mode with 100 kHz filter overlaps almost completely with the DMM2 SAR response.

Fig. 17. 100 V and 1 kV range frequency responses. The DMM2 digitizing mode with 100 kHz filter overlaps almost completely with the DMM2 SAR response.

sine wave amplitude estimation algorithm [31]. A 120 MHz synthesizer bandwidth secured a sine wave level constant enough for the purpose over all applied frequencies up to 20 MHz. A full range voltages were set for 100 mV, 1 and 10 V ranges. A 7.07 V amplitude was used on 100 V and 1 kV ranges, which still provided a reasonable measurement for DMM bandwidths up to 100 kHz or so, despite a significantly decreased signal-to-noise ratio. However, for higher bandwidths on 100 V and 1 kV ranges, the measured results plotted in Fig. 17 show deviation from a smooth low pass filter response. This response might be attributed to the internal DMM2 voltage divider.

The measured responses show almost identical frequency bandwidth between DMM1 DCV mode and DMM2 SAR mode. The DMM2 CB mode provides a very narrow bandwidth of 13.8 kHz, which already impacts a 50 Hz signal by $-6.6 \mu\text{V}/\text{V}$.

C. Distortion

While performing tests in DMM2 CB mode using a precision ČMI SWG03 [11] voltage source and observing the

Fig. 18. DMM2 CB mode and DMM1 DCV mode spectrum while sampling 52 Hz signal with $t_s = 1$ ms, $t_a = 890$ μ s, $N = 4000$ and $M = 4$. Signal source was ČMI SWG03 and signal amplitude was 7 V.

frequency spectrum obtained, two specific results were noted. First was an elevated noise floor at signal frequencies above around 10 Hz due to the internal DMM2 100 ns time jitter (see Fig. 13). Second were a persistent third and fifth harmonic components, being clearly visible in Fig. 18, which plots a spectrum of the same signal obtained by DMM1 and DMM2. Clearly, the DMM2 result is masked by the noise, but it also shows much stronger second, third, and fifth harmonics, which are obviously not present in the signal. Resulting spectrum using DMM1 clearly shows line frequency (50 Hz components up to the fifth harmonic, which is possible due to a very good -151 dB noise floor achieved at the selected sampling parameters.

As it is expected for both DMM1 and DMM2 to be linear far below 1 μ V/V at DC input signal, this result shows that DMM2 CB mode dynamic linearity does not follow this expectation. However, DMM2 DIG mode performs better and shows no signs of increased THD at any frequency. At 1 kHz, it was measured at 0,0025 % using the ČMI SWG03 source. At 110 kHz, it was measured at 0,018 % using the Keysight 33622A source. However, these results present the combined THD of both the source and the sampler and can only be used as a potential performance indication.

V. DMM PHASE RESPONSE

Phase response of a single DMM is usually not of interest and is also never specified by the DMM manufacturer. However, numerous applications for measuring electrical power [19] make direct use of phase measurement using two sampling DMMs. To enable phase measurement, two DMM should be synchronized, either by a common trigger signal or operating in a master–slave fashion. To remove residual phase measurement errors due to various time delays of such setup, a known phase should be measured to provide a reference point. An ideal 0 rad phase reference is a single sine wave signal at a given frequency, which is split to both DMM inputs using equal-length cables. By interchanging the cables between two DMMs and comparing time delay results, the cable and DMM mismatch can be minimized.

While DMM1 DMM has only an external trigger input to facilitate synchronization, DMM2 adds a 1 MHz or 10 MHz

TABLE III
SETTING FOR MASTER–SLAVE PHASE MEASUREMENTS AND RESULTS FOR ZERO PHASE MEASUREMENT. DMM1 AS MASTER AND DMM2 AS SLAVE WERE USED

f	t_a	t_s	Δt_0	$\Delta \phi_0$	$\Delta \phi_{dev}$
52 Hz	195 μ s	220 μ s	1.647 μ s	0.22 μ rad	0.70 μ rad
1 kHz	1.4 μ s	10 μ s	1.668 μ s	2.4 μ rad	1.5 μ rad
19 kHz	1.4 μ s	10 μ s	1.649 μ s	293 μ rad	6.8 μ rad

external clock input, which greatly simplifies synchronous measurements using one or more DMM2. Unfortunately, it does not have any clock output.

To fully evaluate the phase performance of the samplers, one would need to have an ideal phase source, which, of course, is not available. Instead, an arbitrary waveform generator Keysight 33622A and a custom-made ČMI SWG03 high stability DDS source were used. Their performance directly influences the results presented, so the results should be viewed as a superposition of source and sampler results. A few different configurations were used in measurement with an attempt to discriminate which instrument is affecting a nonideal result, with some success.

There are different phase characteristics that can be attributed to a pair of DMMs sampling a two-channel signal. One is a phase linearity over the 2π phase angle at a single frequency, and all sampling parameters (like sampling time, aperture time, range, signal level) being fixed. The other is a phase offset due to a trigger timing misalignment and different input circuitry phase delays, again at these same sampling parameters. Finally, these two characteristics can be measured at different frequencies to obtain their frequency-dependent response. The phase results presented here were not performed thoroughly to give a full picture for either of them, as the equipment used was not available for all those measurements. However, I hope they provide a sneak peek into what is possible to achieve in terms of phase accuracy over a reasonably large frequency bandwidth.

For all phase results presented in this article, 7 V signals were used on 10 V DMMs' range.

A. Master–Slave Synchronization

ČMI SWG03 source was used for these measurements. The settings given in Table III were used. The DMM1 was operating in a DCV mode, while DMM2 was operating in DCV mode only for 52 Hz signal frequency. 100 000 samples were taken for each phase measurement and 10 repetitions were performed at each phase setting. As the DMM1 was used as a master DMM for final results, synchronization was not possible, and thus a PSFE algorithm [31] was used to retrieve phase results.

The following steps were performed.

- 1) A single source channel was connected in parallel to both DMMs using a T-piece and the same length cables. By measuring residual phase, Δt_0 was determined at each frequency, indicating a cumulative time delay between master and slave DMM.

Fig. 19. Phase response at 52 Hz for DMM1 (master) and DMM2 (slave) configuration.

Fig. 20. Phase response at 1 kHz for DMM1 (master) and DMM2 (slave) configuration on 10 V range.

Fig. 21. Phase response at 19 kHz for DMM1 (master) and DMM2 (slave) configuration on 10 V range.

- 2) Source phase was programmed to 0° , both channels were connected to corresponding DMMs, and the phase was measured again, taking into account a residual phase obtained in the previous step (Δt_0). This resulted in a zero phase difference $\Delta\phi_0$.
- 3) Source phase between two channels was increased in steps of 30° to obtain phase linearity results within $\pm\Delta\phi_{\text{dev}}$ as shown in Figs. 19–21. These results are normalized to start from 0 rad. Vertical bars represent standard deviations obtained from ten repetitions at each frequency and phase setting.

A question will certainly appear as to why the DMM1 was used as a master, rendering the clock synchronization impossible. This decision was made based on preliminary experiments, which showed that this configuration is far superior to using DMM2 as a master. This is demonstrated in Fig. 22, where

Fig. 22. Phase response at 1 kHz for DMM2 (master) and DMM1 (slave) configuration on 10 V range.

Fig. 23. Phase response at 1 kHz for DMM1 (master) and DMM2 (slave) configuration on 10 V range. The source had a special function DAC aligned being enabled.

DMM2 served as a master with all other settings remaining exactly the same as for the results shown in Fig. 20, in this case for $f = 1$ kHz. Additionally, the same difference was observed at other signal frequencies.

No further research was done to find the reason for such behavior, and therefore, no explanation can be provided at this point. Unfortunately, no phase measurements were performed with ČMI SWG03 source and two DMM2, as when an operational source arrived, one DMM2 needed to be returned.

Another example is provided here for additional info only. The ČMI SWG03 source software platform offers a DAC alignment mode. This alignment secures a generation of an identical signal even when changing its phase. This is achieved by programming DACs with exactly the same words, regardless of the phase setting. The price paid is that the phase setting resolution is reduced, but the actual phase setting is always reported and could be used as a reference. The results from this experiment are presented in Fig. 23. Comparing this with the results in Fig. 22, we can observe slightly lower standard deviations and slightly better measured phase linearity. There is also a pattern seen on these results, repeating on every $\pi/2$ rad phase change, that also appears in Figs. 20 and 22. This could be related to an effect of high-frequency glitches coming from the source DAC's steps, noting that DAC steps and glitches are hardly filtered out completely.

B. Common Clock Synchronization

For synchronous measurements, two DMM2s were used with a common 10 MHz clock supplied from Keysight 33622A

TABLE IV

SETTING FOR CLOCK SYNCHRONIZED MASTER-SLAVE PHASE MEASUREMENTS AND RESULTS FOR ZERO PHASE MEASUREMENT. TWO DMM2 WERE USED

f	t_a	t_s	Δt_0	$\Delta\phi_0$	$\Delta\phi_{dev}$
1.107 kHz	48 μ s	50 μ s	104.68 ns	-42.7 μ rad	29 μ rad
11.075 kHz	18 μ s	20 μ s	104.73 ns	-6.7 μ rad	36 μ rad
110.75 kHz	0.6 μ s	1 μ s	104.80 ns	49.7 μ rad	15 μ rad
998.7 kHz	0.1 μ s	0.4 μ s	104.82 ns	1375 μ rad	38 μ rad

Fig. 24. Phase response at 1 kHz for two DMM2 using a common external 10 MHz clock and internal TIMER for sampling instants.

Fig. 25. Phase response at 11 kHz for two DMM2 using a common external 10 MHz clock and internal TIMER for sampling instants.

arbitrary waveform synthesizer. They were still configured in a master-slave fashion using Trig Out and Trig In connectors. Both DMMs were configured to operate in digitizing mode, using an SAR DAC. 20 000 samples were taken for each phase measurement and 10 repetitions were performed at each phase setting. The setting given in Table IV were used.

As the sampling was synchronous, all results were obtained using FFT. The same procedure was used as for the master-slave configuration. Results are presented in Figs. 24–27.

While these results are quite promising, they do not show whether source or DMMs are responsible for nonlinearity at 1 and 11 kHz, where the standard deviations are much smaller than this nonlinearity.

VI. CONCLUSION

DMM2 is the first serious challenge to DMM1 dominance in state-of-the-art sampling accuracy at low frequencies. It sports a huge internal memory, all modern interface options, and a clock input for timing synchronization, all lacking in DMM1.

Fig. 26. Phase response at 110 kHz for two DMM2 using a common external 10 MHz clock and internal TIMER for sampling instants.

Fig. 27. Phase response at 1 MHz for two DMM2 using a common external 10 MHz clock and internal TIMER for sampling instants. Measurements performed on 10 V range.

Its functionality limits direct use of its integrating ADC to relatively slow sampling ($f_s \leq 4.7619$ kHz). While its CB path design incorporates zero drift technology, which effectively pushes its $1/f$ noise corner to extremely low frequencies, the price paid is a much elevated white noise floor as well as compromised jitter performance.

For sampling faster signals, DMM2 relies on 18 bit SAR ADC sampling at fixed 5 MHz sampling frequency. For lower sampling frequencies, it mimics the CB sinc response using averaging (see Fig. 15). The performance of this digitizing mode looks excellent, but it no longer holds the same DC accuracy, $1/f$ noise corner, and stability demonstrated by the CB path.

The two DMMs offer a different compromise between $1/f$ noise corner, white noise floor, and high-frequency sampling performance.

VII. FURTHER WORK

It would be interesting to compare the actual DC linearity of DMM1 and DMM2 with a DC Josephson source. Additionally, phase performance should be measured more accurately, as it is quite possible that the results presented here were influenced more by a source than by a DMMs. Certainty, further investigations of this new DMM will reveal its performance in specific areas and applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank Fluke Corporation and Micom to lend two DMM2s for a substantial amount of time, Matjaž Lindič from SIQ for lending DMM1 and 33622A

instruments and Jan Kučera from for lending their SWG03 source. The equipment used in this study was selected solely for measurement purposes; its inclusion does not imply endorsement or preference. They declare no affiliation with or financial interest in the manufacturer of the used equipment.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. L. Swerlein, "A 10 ppm accurate digital AC measurement algorithm," Agilent Technologies, Hewlett-Packard Co. (HP), Loveland, CO, USA, Tech. Rep. Appl. Note 90-A, 1991.
- [2] M. E. Cage, D. Yu, B. M. Jeckelmann, R. L. Steiner, and R. V. Duncan, "Investigating the use of multimeters to measure quantized Hall resistance standards," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 262–266, Apr. 1991.
- [3] S. Svensson, "A precision wattmeter for non-sinusoidal conditions," Dept. Electr. Power Eng., Chalmers Univ. Technol., Gothenburg, Sweden, Tech. Rep. 335L, 1996.
- [4] G. Ramm, H. Moser, and A. Braun, "A new scheme for generating and measuring active, reactive, and apparent power at power frequencies with uncertainties of 2.5×10^{-6} ," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 422–426, Apr. 2011.
- [5] W. G. K. Ihlenfeld, Maintenance and Traceability of AC Voltages By Synchronous Digital Synthesis and Sampling, Standard PTB-Bericht PTB-E-75, 2001.
- [6] E. Mohns, G. Ramm, W. G. K. Ihlenfeld, L. Palafox, and H. Moser, "The PTB primary standard for electrical AC power," *MAPAN*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 15–19, Mar. 2009.
- [7] R. Iuzzolino and W. G. K. Ihlenfeld, "High-accuracy methods and measurement procedures for power quality parameters using the digital synchronous sampling technique," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 426–430, Apr. 2007.
- [8] P. Espel, A. Poletaef, and A. Bounouh, "Characterization of analogue-to-digital converters of a commercial digital voltmeter in the 20 Hz to 400 Hz frequency range," *Metrologia*, vol. 46, no. 5, pp. 578–584, Oct. 2009.
- [9] P. Horowitz and W. Hill, *The Art of Electronics*. Cambridge, U.K.: Cambridge Univ. Press, 2015.
- [10] R. Lapuh, J. Kučera, J. Kováč, and B. Voljč, "Digital multimeters sampling performance comparison," in *Proc. Conf. Precis. Electromagn. Meas.*, 2024, pp. 1–2.
- [11] J. Kučera, J. Kováč, L. Palafox, R. Behr, and L. Vojáčková, "Characterization of a precision modular sinewave generator," *Meas. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 31, no. 6, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 064002.
- [12] *Keysight Trueform Series Waveform Generator, Operating and Service Guide*, Keysight Technol., Santa Rosa, CA, USA, Nov. 2020.
- [13] *3457A Multimeter Operating Manual*, Hewlett-Packard Co., Loveland, CO, USA, May 1986.
- [14] *Hewlett-Packard Journal*, Hewlett-Packard Co., Palo Alto, CA, USA, Apr. 1987.
- [15] *A/D Converter Technology*, Fluke Calibration, Everett, WA, USA, 2019.
- [16] *8588A/8558A Reference Multimeter and 8 (1/2) Digit Multimeter Operators Manual*, Fluke Calibration, Everett, WA, USA, Feb. 2019.
- [17] *8588A Reference Multimeter Product Specifications, Rev. B, 4/19*, Fluke Calibration, Everett, WA, USA, Mar. 2019.
- [18] W. C. Goecke, "An 8 (1/2)-digit integrating analog-to-digital converter with 16-bit, 100,000-sample-per-second performance," *Hewlett-Packard J.*, vol. 40, pp. 8–15, May 1989.
- [19] R. Lapuh, *Sampling with 3458A, Understanding, Programming, Sampling and Signal Processing*. Ljubljana, Slovenia: Left Right D.O.O, 2018.
- [20] R. Lapuh, B. Voljč, and M. Lindic, "Keysight 3458A noise performance," in *Proc. Conf. Precis. Electromagn. Meas. (CPEM)*, Jul. 2016, pp. 1–2.
- [21] P. Welch, "The use of fast Fourier transform for the estimation of power spectra: A method based on time averaging over short, modified periodograms," *IEEE Trans. Audio Electroacoustics*, vol. AE-15, no. 2, pp. 70–73, Jun. 1967.
- [22] N. Beev, M. C. Bastos, M. Martino, D. Valuch, L. Palafox, and R. Behr, "Design and metrological characterization of a digitizer for the highest precision magnet powering in the high luminosity large hadron collider," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 73, pp. 1–10, 2024.
- [23] D. Drung et al., "Validation of the ultrastable low-noise current amplifier as travelling standard for small direct currents," *Metrologia*, vol. 52, no. 6, pp. 756–763, Oct. 2015.
- [24] F. Stein et al., "Robustness of single-electron pumps at sub-ppm current accuracy level," *Metrologia*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. S1–S8, Feb. 2017.
- [25] T. Friederichs, "Analysis of geodetic time series using Allan variances," Universität Stuttgart, Geodätisches Institut, Tech. 2010.
- [26] W. J. Riley, "Handbook of frequency stability analysis," NIST, Stuttgart, Germany, Tech. Rep., 2008.
- [27] R. Lapuh, B. Voljč, and M. Lindic, "Evaluation of agilent 3458A time jitter performance," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 64, no. 6, pp. 1331–1335, Jun. 2015.
- [28] R. Lapuh and R. Lapuh, "Keysight 3458A frequency response model identification," in *Proc. Conf. Precis. Electromagn. Meas. (CPEM)*, Jul. 2018, pp. 1–2.
- [29] S. W. Smith. (1997). *The Scientist & Engineer' S Guide To Digital Signal Processing*. [Online]. Available: <http://www.dspguide.com/>
- [30] G. B. Gubler, "Reconstruction of bandlimited signal using samples obtained from integration digital voltmeters," in *Proc. CPEM*, Jun. 2010, pp. 257–258.
- [31] R. Lapuh, "Estimating the fundamental component of harmonically distorted signals from noncoherently sampled data," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 64, no. 6, pp. 1419–1424, Jun. 2015.
- [32] J. Schoukens, R. Pintelon, and G. Vandersteen, "A sinewave fitting procedure for characterizing data acquisition channels in the presence of time base distortion and time jitter," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 1005–1010, Aug. 1997.